

Human Resource Management Practices in Private Commercial Banking Sector: (A Study on Khulna City, Bangladesh)

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Abstract

"Human Resources" is a comparatively newer field of management study. Previously it was called "personnel management". Human resource management deals with any aspects of any organization that affects employees, such as hiring and firing, pay, benefits, training, and administration. Every bank operating in Khulna city has its own mission to sustain in the banking sector as a customer and profit oriented organization. And the mission statements reflect the strategies, goals and the overall approach of organizations. In this study we have tried to find out how HRM practices in banking sector in Khulna region. Our study is divided into some key factors regarding to the human resources aspects including recruitment and hiring, training and development, compensation management, work time and environment, performance appraisal, and motivation at work. However, with the aid of a structured survey questionnaire, we collected data and analyze those with different statistical tools and techniques. Moreover, this study is based on human resources management practices in private commercial banks in Bangladesh. Therefore, the research convenience we have taken only employees of the branches operating in Khulna city.

Keywords: Recruitment and Hiring, Training and Development, Compensation System, Motivation, Performance Appraisal.

CHAPTER- 1: INTRODUCTION:

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY:

This report is prepared as a requirement of the course "Human Resource Management." We selected 14 private commercial banks of Khulna. Working on these organizations we came to know various kind of HRM practice which is used here. In this report we have followed the guidelines provided by the teacher. Here we have tasked not only the HRM practice but also the marketing, management, finance and operational area of the Company. The concept of Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) originated in the U.S.A. just after the development of the concept of Human Resource Management (HRM) in the 1960s and 1970s. Schuler (1989) argues that organizations need to develop HRM practices that lead to the development of an employee role behavior that is supportive of the strategy it adopts. This in turn will influence the organization's performance. Achieving congruence between HRM practice and strategy is one of the key emphases of the strategic HRM theory. It is also argued that given certain characteristics of the service firms, they should develop a more strategic HRM practice than manufacturing firms. So, since SHRM emergence it has been adopted increasingly around the world. In spite of the relatively widespread acceptance of the theory there is very little evidence of its existence in practice. The traditional roles of the people management function can be described as reactive and focused on operational matters and they are typically found in the public sector personnel management functions. Today the people management function has been accepted as a key factor in the structural reforms caused by commercialization and corporatization. Therefore, the status and influence of the HRM function is considered to be critical in the process,

especially in achieving the link between the people management function and the strategic management process. The effectiveness of SHRM can be explained by examining the contributions of the people management function in the process of achieving strategic integration. It is thus expected that after adopting SHRM in our banking sector there will be an improvement in the overall level of HRM effectiveness. Banks are critical element in any economy. As a developing country, the banking sector serves as the main sources of resource mobilization. Due to undeveloped money market and capital market, limited availability of financial instrument, and lack of confidence in financial system bank becomes the dominant financial intermediary to broad segment of population of our country. And at this situation private banks are performing the major role. As banks are act as intermediaries in case of transaction so they also deal with the variety of risk. But the practices of SHRM will help bank to operate without excessive risk exposures and provide a healthy financial system. In case of banking sector HQ units play two major functions, namely value creation and administration. This implies that the HQ unit is expected to contribute administratively while the other function contributes strategically to the strategic management process. We see that HR departments in commercialized sector organizations focus on those roles that have strategic implications.

Therefore, the study has drawn on "Human Resource Management Practices in Private Commercial Banking Sector:(A Study on Khulna City, Bangladesh)"models of appropriate environment initiatives for the purposes of

increasing the knowledge base and strengthening the capacity to develop or improve the existing programs in this area.

Finally, our main objective is to investigate the aspects of SHRM processes and outcomes to evaluations the effectiveness of the HR unit in case of achieving the organization goal.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

Objective of the Study that are selected are listed below:

1. To identify the implementation of key Human Resources Management practices in the sample banks.
2. To identify the nature extent of relationship between Compensation system and Performance Appraisal.
3. To identify the nature and extent of relationship between Human Resources Management Practices and level of motivation.
4. To determine the motivation level of the employees.
5. To identify the effect of Human Resources Management Practice on employee motivation.

1.3 HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

Hypothesis – I : Human resources practices are not properly implemented in Banks.

Hypothesis – II : Human resources practices are properly implemented in Banks.

Hypothesis -III: Properly practiced human resources management does not motivate employees.

Hypothesis-IV: Properly practiced human resources management motivates employees.

1.4 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

Since the study concentrates only on handful organizations, findings may not give the accurate and total picture of all organizations. Besides, no human resources management department in Khulna branches. However, top level managers are dealing with the HRM practice. Furthermore, all the employees are bias to their organization and it may derive the calculated result from the real scenario.

1.5 REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Human resources management is the process of acquiring, training, appraising, and compensating employees, and of attending to their labor relations, health and safety, and fairness concerns. Like management process, it has some basic functions like planning, organizing, staffing, leading and controlling in forms of recruitment & selection, training & development, compensation, employee relations, etc.

Developments in the field of Human Resource Management are now well documented in the literature (see Legge, 1995; Schuler, 2000; Schuler and Jackson, 1999; Sisson and Storey, 2000). As firms are entering into a more dynamic world of international business and as the globalization of world markets continues apace, comparative HRM issues appear to be gaining momentum. Both practitioners and academics in the field of HRM are increasingly aware of the need to

examine and understand the HRM system suitable to different parts of the world. They are also interested in finding relevant HRM policies and practices for different types of organizations (for example, public/private sector, manufacturing/service sector) around the globe. HRM practices are central to improving the quality of services offered by the governments. In the words of Pfeffer (1994), 'having good HRM is likely to generate much loyalty, commitment or willingness to expend extra effort for the organization's objectives'. Moreover, Stone (1998) remarks that 'HRM is either part of the problem or part of the solution in gaining the productive contribution of people'.

In this study, the most relevant HRM domains (e.g. selection, training, job description, performance appraisal system, compensation system career planning system and employee participation) are selected for research. In the field of human resource management and behavioral sciences, plenty of example and discussions are highlighting that there is an uplifting connection between effective HRM practices and organizational performance (Deepak et al., 2003; Sels et al., 2003; Singh, 2004). Qureshi et al. (2007) explored the positive effect of selection ($r = 0.53$), performance appraisal ($r = 0.55$), training ($r = 0.61$), compensation system ($r = 0.39$) and employee participation ($r = 0.46$) with organizational performance. Out of these practices, only selection ($b = 0.27, 0.30$), training ($b = 0.31, 0.28$) and employee participation ($b = 0.19, 0.26$) had positive impacts on organizational performance and market performance of the organization. This indicated that an increase of 1 unit in selection will increase firm performance by 0.27 and firm market performance by 0.30; secondly, an increase of 1 unit in training will increase firm performance by 0.31 and firms market performance by 0.28. Finally, an increase of 1 unit in employee participation will increase firm performance by 0.19 and firm market performance by 0.26. Supporting these findings, Singh (2004) found that there is a positive relationship amongst several HR practices like selection ($r = 0.32$), performance appraisal ($r = 0.32$), training ($r = 0.32$), compensation system ($r = 0.32$) employee participation ($r = 0.32$) with firm performance. Out of these practices, only training ($b = 0.37, 0.39$) and compensation system ($b = 0.41, 0.43$) had positive impacts on firm performance and market performance of the firm. This indicated that an increase of 1 unit in training will increase firm performances by 0.37 and firm market performance by 0.39; secondly, an increase of 1 unit in compensation will increase firm performance by 0.41 and 0.43 in a firm's market performance. On the other hand, two practices namely, job definition ($b = -0.21$) and career planning system ($b = -0.15$) have a negative and insignificant impact on firm performance. Deepak et al. (2003) concluded that organizational performance and competitiveness can be enhanced by utilizing high performance work system. This study using regression (95% level of confidence) analysis, it is identified that relative use of HR practices displays stronger association with organizational performance and employee motivation. Supporting the same arguments, Arthur (1994) found that steel mills that use an HRM 'Commitment System' have higher productivity levels than those that do not. HPW system has significant positive effects on organization productivity.

Huselid (1995), in his study of 968 US companies, identified a positive link between HRM practices and firm performance. One standard deviation increase in HRM practices increases firm performance by 25%. Wan et al. (2002) examined the relationship between HRM practices and firm performance. HRM practices were creating positive effect on organizational performance. Results calculated through regression suggested that effective implementation of key HRM practices increases organizational performance. On the other hand, companies interested in enhancing HR performance may emphasize the need for empowerment and training. Few studies, however, did not find clear effects of HRM practices on productivity (Delaney et al., 1989). Kelley (1996) found that HRM practices do not affect performance of organizations; Batt (2002) found that HRM practices do not pay off in small organizations that operate in local markets. Cappelli and Newmark (2001) identified that human resource management practices may raise productivity slightly, but they also raise labor costs. Huselid (1995) evaluated that HRM practices are statistically significant and having positive effect on corporate financial performance of the organization. Numerous researchers found the relationship between corporate financial performance and HRM practices. Motivated employees in the workplace can be termed as those who willingly and voluntarily extend their best efforts in order to help the organization attaining its goals. Motivated employees are sincere, dutiful, hard working; therefore need less supervision to exert best performance out of them Uddin,A.T.M.J, Nabi,M.N, Hasan,S.M.(2004).

In the article of Wilkinson, Adrian 'Towards HRM? A Case Study from Banking' presents the literature on management strategy and employee relations and the rise of HRM to give a clear view about SHRM. This work is on the co-operative banks to show how the combination of product market change, and increasing recognition of the inadequacy of the old style approach to the management of labor led to the embracing of a more pro-active role to managing human resources through adopting SHRM. It explores the development of HRM in the co-operative bank. It also focused on the response of the bank to changes in financial sector which has been experiencing deregulation, increasing competition, technological innovation; change from personnel management to HRM.

Few things are more important to a company's long-term performance than choosing the right employees and ensuring they have the proper outlook from Day One. As a result, employers should view the recruitment and orientation process as an opportunity, not as a burden. Preparing employees for their new roles and communicating how they can help the firm meet its goals can go a long way toward determining whether new employees ultimately succeed (Ilene Gochman, 2007).

Flamholtz (1985) and Cascio (1991) concluded that financial returns associated with investments in progressive HRM practices are generally substantial. Schmidt et al. (1979) explored that increasing one unit of employee performance is equivalent to 40% of salary increase. Each of these studies has

emphasized on the impact of human resource management practices on organizational performance.

The present study on "Human Resource Management Practices in Private Commercial Banking Sector : (A Study on Khulna City, Bangladesh)" may identifies the extent of HRM practices in Banking sectors in Bangladesh in employee motivation and organizational performance.

CHAPTER- 2: MATERIALS AND METHOD:

2.1 SAMPLING DESIGN:

Under this report we consider all sorts of HRM practices in the banking sector of Khulna city. It bases on the information provided by the employees of 14 major private banks of the city to find out the related factors to meet the organizational goals are developed in employees. However, for preparing this study we mainly depend on primary data which was collected through direct survey. We developed a questionnaire which consisted of 40 close ended questions and mainly focusing on strategic human resource management practices in banking sector of Bangladesh specially in Khulna region.

Therefore, Data was collected from employees of different banks in Khulna city. We took different type of employee randomly who work in different banks in the city. Our sample size was 115. The survey is conducted through face to face interview. Our study findings come out by analyzing these primary data.

Here we use Likert scale which consists of 1 to 5. Here, 5 point for "To a great level", 4 point for "To a small level", 3 point for "Not sure", 2 point for "To some level" and 1 point for "Not at all".

SAMPLE SIZE:

Primarily, we have selected only the private commercial banks for the judgmental sampling respondent. Our sample size is 115. We have selected 14 banks among which we have taken 115 employees as our respondents. And the banks are:

List of Private Commercial Banks Surveyed in the Study:

Table- 1. List of Private Commercial Banks

SL No.	Name of Bank
01.	AB Bank Limited
02.	Islami Bank Limited
03.	Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited
04.	Bank Asia Limited
05.	BRAC Bank Limited
06.	City Bank Limited
07.	Eastern Bank Limited
08.	EXIM Bank Limited
09.	IFIC Bank Limited
10.	Premier Bank Limited
11.	Mercantile Bank Limited
12.	Prime Bank Limited
13.	Standard Chartered Bank Limited
14.	Shahjalal Islamic Bank Limited

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Finally, I have solved the solution with equation of Arithmetic Mean, Grand Mean, Standard Deviation, Hypothesis test and Correlation coefficient,

$$(1) \text{ Arithmetic Mean, } \bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N} \text{-----(1)}$$

$$\text{Or, } \bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N}$$

$$(2) \text{ Grand Mean, } \mu_x = \frac{\bar{X}}{N} \text{-----(2)}$$

$$(3) \text{ Standard Deviation, } \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} \text{-----(3)}$$

$$(4) \sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} \text{-----(4)}$$

$$(5) Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} \text{-----(5)}$$

$$(6) \text{ Correlation coefficient, } r = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} \text{-----(6)}$$

Here, $X = x - \bar{X}$, $y = y - \bar{Y}$

$$(7) \text{ Regression equation of Y on X : } (Y - \bar{Y}) = b_{yx}(X - \bar{X}) \text{---(7)}$$

$$(8) \text{ Regression equation of X on Y : } (X - \bar{X}) = b_{xy}(Y - \bar{Y}) \text{---(8)}$$

Here, $b_{yx} = \frac{\sum xy}{\sum x^2}$ and $b_{xy} = \frac{\sum xy}{\sum y^2}$

2.2 DATA COLLECTION AND METHOD:

The process of data collection has been categorized into two sources:

- 1) Primary data sources
- 2) Secondary data sources

Primary Data Sources:

Survey questionnaire is prepared and respondents are selected randomly and interviewing the respondents. We developed a questionnaire that consisted of 16(Sixteen)close ended questions mainly focusing on the key dimensions of human resources management including Recruitment & Selection, Training & Development, Performance Appraisal, Compensation systems, Flexible work arrangements and some key areas of Motivation practices in banking sector of Bangladesh especially in Khulna region.

Secondary Data Sources:

In this study secondary data is also used. Some Published Journals and Internet are the main sources of such information.

Data Processing:

The collected data is presented through tables and figures. Here we have used for presenting data and using statistical tools like Mean, Standard Deviation, Normal distribution chart (Z-test), Regression and Correlation analysis are used. For normal distribution analysis we are taking 95% confidence level i.e. 5% significance level.

The calculation for any particular statement can be shown by the following table:

Table -2. Particular Statement

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5			
To some level	4			
Not sure	3			
To a small level	2			
Not at all	1			
Total		N=	$\sum(fx) =$	

For representing a deliberate picture of the total responses the following scales will be used:

Table -3. Deliberate picture of the total responses

No.	Range of Mean	Representation
I.	$5.00 \geq \text{Mean} \leq 4.51$	Represents “ Most Favorable ” standing of the respondents towards a specific statement
II.	$4.50 \geq \text{Mean} \leq 3.51$	Represents “ Favorable ” standing of the respondents towards a specific statement
III.	$3.50 \geq \text{Mean} \leq 3.00$	Represents “ Moderate ” standing of the respondents towards a specific statement
IV.	$2.99 \geq \text{Mean} \leq 1.00$	Represents “ Negative ” standing of the respondents towards a specific statement

CHAPTER- 3: ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS:

3.1: Identifying the implementation of Human Resources Management practices

Table-4:Statistical data of Human Resource Management practice

Key areas of HRM Practice	Mean of Each Area	Standard Deviation (σ)	Grand Mean (μ_x)	Z value	σ_x
Recruitment and Hiring	3.711	9.26	3.661	0.012	4.141
Training and Development	3.791	8.758		0.033	3.916
Performance Appraisal	3.634	9.426		-0.006	4.215
Compensation Systems	3.973	9.262		0.075	4.142
Flexible work Arrangement	3.2	6.519		-0.158	2.915

arrangement is less than -1.96. Other z values are within the limit of critical z values at 5% level of significance (± 1.96). So, we can say HRM practice is properly implemented in first four key areas.

The average z value of these five key areas are negative which is also within the critical value of z for two tailed test at 5% level of significance (± 1.96). So, null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Thus in cases of objective 1 we can conclude that, Human resources practices are properly implemented in Banks.

Figure-2 : Percentage of employee respondents

First, consider our first objective. In order to identify the Human resource management implementation we consider five key areas of Human resource management (Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development, Performance Appraisal, Compensation system and Flexible work Arrangement). In case of identification descriptive statistical tools such as Mean value (Mean), frequency, standard deviation and normal distribution (z test) have been used. Mean value of each key area is shown in the above table 4. In comparison with the range of table 3 we can say recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal and compensation system areas are in favorable situation. But flexible work arrangement area is in moderate situation. The grand mean value depicts that the average mean value (3.661) of these five key areas remains in the range of $4.50 \geq \text{Mean} \geq 3.51$. So, it is determined that the HRM practice in banks of Khulna is in "Favorable" situation (according to table 3).

Figure-1: Normal distribution curve at 5% level of significance ($z = \pm 1.96$)

We have also considered normal distribution (z test) to determine the human resource management practice. At 5% level of significance the critical value of z for two-tailed test = ± 1.96 . If the computed value of z is greater than +1.96 or less than -1.96 then hypothesis is rejected, otherwise accepted. As we have modulated the human resource management practice in five key areas so we have calculated five z test value (each one for each area) which is shown in the above table. From the table we can see that only the z value of flexible work

13%

According to our survey among 115 employees around 41% strongly agrees and 28% agrees that human resource management is practiced in Banks of Khulna city. Around 7% disagrees and 13% strongly disagrees with them. The rest of the employees are neutral about this statement.

3.2: Relationship between Compensation system and Performance Appraisal

In order to accomplish our second objective we used correlation method of statistics. There is a very high degree of positive correlation between compensation systems and performance appraisal (+0.985) with mean 3.973 and 3.634 respectively, which indicate that most of employees are idealizing performance appraisal as an important factor which is directly correlated with compensation system. The

calculated regression equation of compensation system(Y) on performance appraisal (X) is –
 $Y = 1.09X$

Figure-3. Graphical representation of regression equation

of compensation system(Y) on performance appraisal (X)
3.3: Relationship between human resource management practice and motivation at work

According to our calculation human resource management practice and motivation at work is highly correlated with each other (as correlation coefficient of HRM and motivation, $r = +0.9995$). It indicates that human resource management practice has an effective impact on motivation of employees. The regression equation of HRM practice (X) on Motivation (Y) is –
 $X = 0.98Y - 0.0132$

Figure-4. Graphical representation of regression equation of Motivation(X) on Human Resource Management Practice (Y)

3.4: Motivation level of the employees

Our fourth objective is to determine the motivation level of employees. For this purpose eleven key areas of motivation are considered. In this case statistical such as Mean value (Mean) and standard deviation is used. Mean value of each key area is shown in below the following table 5. According to the range of above table 3 we can say third area is in most favorable situation, seven areas (First, second, fifth, sixth, ninth, tenth and eleventh) are in favorable situation, eighth area is in moderate situation and only the seventh area is in negative situation. The grand mean value depicts that the average mean value (3.778) of these eleven key areas remains in the range of $4.50 \geq \text{Mean} \geq 3.51$. So, it is determined that the motivation level of the employees is in “Favorable” situation (according to table 3).

Table-5: Statistical data for determining motivation level

Area No	Mean of Each Area	Result	Standard Deviation (σ)	Grand Mean (μ_x)	Z Value	σ_x
1.	4.347	Favorable	12.42	3.778	0.151	3.744
2.	4.15	Favorable	9.605		0.128	2.896
3.	4.60	Most Favorable	14.74		0.184	4.444
4.	2.226	Negative	8.723		-0.590	2.630
5.	4.278	Favorable	10.704		0.154	3.227
6.	4.034	Favorable	9.568		0.088	2.884
7.	2.904	Negative	6.861		-0.422	2.068
8.	3.191	Moderate	7.804		-0.249	2.353
9.	3.669	Favorable	7.688		-0.047	2.318
10.	4.330	Favorable	10.621		0.172	3.202
11.	3.834	Favorable	7.178		0.025	2.164

3.5: Effect of Human Resources Management Practice on employee motivation

Finally, consider objective 5. Here normal distribution (z test) is applied to identify the effect of Human Resources Management Practice and employee motivation. For this identification eleven z test value (each one for each area) have been calculated which is shown in the table 5. From the table we can see that only the z values of First to eleventh areas remain within the critical z value at 5% level of significance (± 1.96). As most of the cases z values indicates that properly practiced human resource management motivate employees. So we can say that alternate hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted.

CHAPTER-4:
CONCLUSION AND RECOMANDATION:
CONCLUSION:

Basically to find out the overall practices of human resource management in the banking sector of our country need more research work and strong influence. However, we couldn't sharpen our observation and analysis of our paper for this lack. Managers are passing a hard time, and their works are not being easier. But what we can see in the banking industry there human resource management system is only in a name. They don't participate into the overall management systems. And those systems also have problems behind this issue. It should be kept in mind that efficient employees of an organization is the assets of that organization and that is why it should be taken up carefully. If they can meet up their shortage they will do much better in the banking sector in Bangladesh. Therefore, we are so much grateful to those employees who give us time to conduct our survey.

RECOMANDATIONS:

After completion the study we have gathered some practical knowledge about the Human Resource practices in Private Commercial Banking Sector. Moreover, we would like to provide some recommendations, which might be helpful to upgrade the Human Resource practice of Private Commercial Banking Sector is given below:

1. First of all the main important thing for an organization is the Recruitment, which exists in this bank, is not well designed. They can also go for online recruitment, which is a modern method.
2. From the point of Training it can be said that their training course is well but not that much practical. They provide training to their employees in their training institute or send them to BIBM (Bangladesh Institute of Bank Management) which is one of the reputed institutions for the bankers to be trained up. In this sort of training they usually get theoretical idea. In this case they can also arrange on the job training which will enable the employees to learn more effectively.
3. The bank does not have compensation for its employees which is low comparatively very low in the organization, which should be increased.
4. There should be also option for reward system which is not present in this bank.
5. Employees are satisfied with their respective organizations' human resource management system, but there may be confusion about the position distribution of the employees. Maybe they think of redistribution.
6. Recruitment and selection procedures are well enough, and training is also better provided.
7. Employees are not concerned about advocacy and employee laws. But they are feeling comfortable with the internal communication process and employee treatment from the management.
8. Overall human resource management needs to be improved.

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2	-1	-6	36
1	-2	-26	676
		$\sum fd = 97$	$\sum fd^2 = 9957$

Here, A=3,N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N} = 3.711$

(b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} = 9.26$ (c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 4.141$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.012$

Training and Development:

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	42	210	3.791
To some level	4	37	148	
Not sure	3	15	45	
To a small level	2	12	24	
Not at all	1	9	9	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 436$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	84	7056
4	1	37	1369
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-12	144
1	-2	-18	324
		$\sum fd = 91$	$\sum fd^2 = 8893$

Here, A=3,N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N} = 3.791$

(b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} = 8.758$ (c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 3.916$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.033$

Performance Appraisal:

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	46	230	3.634
To some level	4	26	104	
Not sure	3	13	39	
To a small level	2	15	30	
Not at all	1	15	15	

APPENDIX A:

Recruitment and Hiring:

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Point s (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	43	215	3.711
To some level	4	43	172	
Not sure	3	10	30	
To a small level	2	6	12	
Not at all	1	13	13	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 442$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	86	7396
4	1	43	1849
3	0	0	0

Total		N= 115	$\Sigma fx = 41$ 8
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$$(b) \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\Sigma fd}{n}\right)^2} = 9.262$$

$$(c) \sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 4.142$$

$$(d) Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.075$$

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	92	8464
4	1	26	676
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-15	225
1	-2	-30	900
		$\Sigma fd = 73$	$\Sigma fd^2 = 10265$

Here, A=3, N=115

$$(a) \bar{X} = A + \frac{\Sigma fd}{N} = 3.634$$

$$(b) \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\Sigma fd}{n}\right)^2} = 9.426$$

$$(c) \sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 4.215$$

$$(d) Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = -0.006$$

Compensation System:

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\Sigma fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	47	235	3.973
To some level	4	32	128	
Not sure	3	27	81	
To a small level	2	4	8	
Not at all	1	5	5	
Total		N= 115	$\Sigma fx = 457$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	94	8836
4	1	32	1024
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-4	16
1	-2	-10	100
		$\Sigma fd = 112$	$\Sigma fd^2 = 9976$

Here, A=3, N=115

$$(a) \bar{X} = A + \frac{\Sigma fd}{N} = 3.973$$

Flexible Work arrangement:

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\Sigma fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	19	95	3.2
To some level	4	41	164	
Not sure	3	18	54	
To a small level	2	18	36	
Not at all	1	19	19	
Total		N= 115	$\Sigma fx = 368$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	38	1444
4	1	41	1681
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-18	324
1	-2	-38	1444
		$\Sigma fd = 23$	$\Sigma fd^2 = 4893$

Here, A=3, N=115

$$(a) \bar{X} = A + \frac{\Sigma fd}{N} = 3.2$$

$$(b) \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\Sigma fd}{n}\right)^2} = 6.519$$

$$(c) \sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 2.915$$

$$(d) Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = -0.158$$

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	45	225	4.15
To some level	4	51	204	
Not sure	3	11	33	
To a small level	2	8	16	
Not at all	1	0	0	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 478$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	90	8100
4	1	51	2601
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-8	64
1	-2	0	0
		$\sum fd = 133$	$\sum fd^2 = 10765$

Here, A=3,N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N} = 4.15$ (b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} = 9.605$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 2.896$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.128$

**APPENDIX B:
Motivation Level of the Employees:**

No. (1)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	65	325	4.347
To some level	4	32	128	
Not sure	3	13	39	
To a small level	2	3	6	
Not at all	1	2	2	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 500$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	130	16900
4	1	32	1024
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-3	9
1	-2	-4	16
		$\sum fd = 155$	$\sum fd^2 = 17949$

Here, A=3,N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N} = 4.347$

(b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} = 12.42$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 3.744$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.151$

No. (2)

No. (3)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	78	390	4.60
To some level	4	31	124	
Not sure	3	4	12	
To a small level	2	2	4	
Not at all	1	0	0	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 530$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	156	24336
4	1	31	961
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-2	4
1	-2	0	0
		$\sum fd = 185$	$\sum fd^2 = 25301$

Here, A=3,N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N} = 4.60$ (b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} = 14.74$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 4.444$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.184$

No. (4)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	4	20	2.226
To some level	4	20	80	
Not sure	3	17	51	
To a small level	2	31	62	
Not at all	1	43	43	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 256$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	8	24336
4	1	20	961
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-31	4
1	-2	-86	0
		$\sum fd = -89$	$\sum fd^2 = 8821$

Here, A=3, N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N} = 2.226$ (b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} = 8.723$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 2.630$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = -0.590$

No. (5)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	52	260	4.278
To some level	4	50	200	
Not sure	3	6	18	
To a small level	2	7	14	
Not at all	1	0	0	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 492$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	104	10816
4	1	50	2500
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-7	49
1	-2	0	0
		$\sum fd = 147$	$\sum fd^2 = 13365$

Here, A=3, N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N} = 4.278$ (b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} = 10.704$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 3.227$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.154$

No. (6)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	47	235	4.034
To some level	4	41	164	
Not sure	3	16	48	
To a small level	2	6	12	
Not at all	1	5	5	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 464$	

Proof:

	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	94	8836
4	1	41	1681
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-6	36
1	-2	-10	100
		$\sum fd = 119$	$\sum fd^2 = 10653$

Here, A=3, N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N} = 4.034$ (b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} = 9.568$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 2.884$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.088$

No. (7)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	18	90	2.904
To some level	4	33	132	
Not sure	3	14	42	
To a small level	2	20	40	
Not at all	1	30	30	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 334$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	36	1296

4	1	33	1089
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-20	400
1	-2	-60	3600
		$\Sigma fd = -11$	$\Sigma fd^2 = 6385$

Here, A=3,N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\Sigma fd}{N} = 2.904$ (b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\Sigma fd}{n}\right)^2} = 6.86$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 2.068$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = -0.422$

No. (8)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\Sigma fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	30	150	3.191
To some level	4	30	120	
Not sure	3	9	27	
To a small level	2	24	48	
Not at all	1	22	22	
Total		N= 115	$\Sigma fx = 367$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	60	3600
4	1	30	900
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-24	576
1	-2	-44	1936
		$\Sigma fd = 22$	$\Sigma fd^2 = 7012$

Here, A=3,N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\Sigma fd}{N} = 3.191$ (b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\Sigma fd}{n}\right)^2} = 7.806$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 2.353$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = -0.249$

No. (9)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\Sigma fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	29	145	3.669
To some level	4	53	212	
Not sure	3	11	33	
To a small level	2	10	20	
Not at all	1	12	12	
Total		N= 115	$\Sigma fx = 422$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	58	3364
4	1	53	2809
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-10	100
1	-2	-24	576
		$\Sigma fd = 77$	$\Sigma fd^2 = 6849$

Here, A=3,N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\Sigma fd}{N} = 3.669$ (b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\Sigma fd}{n}\right)^2} = 7.688$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 2.318$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = -0.047$

No. (10)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\Sigma fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	52	260	4.330
To some level	4	55	220	
Not sure	3	2	6	
To a small level	2	6	12	
Not at all	1	0	0	
Total		N= 115	$\Sigma fx = 498$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	104	10116
4	1	55	3025
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-6	36
1	-2	0	0
		$\Sigma fd = 153$	$\Sigma fd^2 = 13177$

Here, A=3,N=115

(a) $\bar{X} = A + \frac{\Sigma fd}{N} = 4.330$ (b) $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\Sigma fd}{n}\right)^2} = 10.621$

(c) $\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 3.202$ (d) $Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.172$

No. (11)

Options in Scale	Value (x)	Frequency of Respondents (f)	Total Points (fx)	Mean $\bar{X} = \frac{\Sigma fx}{N}$
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				$\frac{\sum fx}{N}$
To a great level	5	32	160	3.834
To some level	4	43	172	
Not sure	3	32	96	
To a small level	2	5	10	
Not at all	1	3	3	
Total		N= 115	$\sum fx = 441$	

Proof:

X	d= X-A	fd	fd ²
5	2	64	4096
4	1	43	1849
3	0	0	0
2	-1	-5	25
1	-2	-6	36
		$\sum fd = 96$	$\sum fd^2 = 6006$

Here, A=3,N=115

$$(a) \bar{X} = A + \frac{\sum fd}{N} = 3.834 \quad (b) \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{n}\right)^2} = 7.178$$

$$(c) \sigma_x = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} = 2.164 \quad (d) Z = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu_x)}{\sigma_x} = 0.025$$

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Bank Map of Selected Area in Khulna City, Bangladesh.

